

EVERYDAY INTERACTIVE-KINETIC ENVIRONMENTS: EXAMPLES IN LATIN AMERICA

FORMATTING GUIDELINES FOR PAPER SUBMISSIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to study characteristics present in the development of interactive-kinetic environments in Latin America. For this purpose, a variety of examples are examined. These serve to illustrate the means employed in Latin America to achieve 'high-social' interaction with the appropriate use of available resources. The paper begins with a brief introduction of the existing heritage of interactive-kinetic environments in Latin America and their links to architecture. It supports the argument that architecture and urban space in Latin American can be enriched by generating meaningful and active interactions between people and their environment. A reflection on future horizons on the field concludes the paper.

KEYWORDS: *transformable, kinetic, interactive environments*

BACKGROUND

Interactive-kinetic environments create conditions where the architectural space and/or building fabric can engage in communication with its inhabitants through the use of kinetic and sensory components. In so doing, architecture meets the need of all senses by stimulating tactile, auditory, olfactory and/or visual engagement. This type of interaction relies on both the physical and intangible elements that shape space, instigating a type of architecture that encourages the emergence of new social dynamics. The transformative nature of human interaction, which fuels interactive-kinetic environments, allows the experience of a space to change constantly. This could generate an open type of exchange that goes beyond ordinary participation, where the actors engage in and achieve a deeper and evolving conversation. In this context, traditional architectural systems of production and consumption are altered. Architecture becomes not an end result, but a tool that allows input and output processing. Architects design tools to be used by the inhabitants for the construction of their environment. Hence people are more committed and responsible for the space that they inhabit.

Interactive-kinetic environments have their origins in interactive and kinetic art sculptures and installations of the beginning of the 20th century. One of the earliest examples was

Rotative Plaques Verre, Optique de Précision (1920) by French artist Marcel Duchamp, a sculpture where the viewer was required to initiate a mechanism and stand at a distance in order to see an optical illusion generated by its movement. Further development of kinetic art mobiles and sculptures took place during the 1950s with the work of Russian artists Vladimir Tatlin and Aleksander Rodchenko and American sculptor Alexander Calder. Their experimental endeavours introduced ways to control movement through the use of technological enhancements. Early interactive-kinetic interventions generally remained close to the geometric abstraction at the beginning of the 20th century. Their materialisation was mainly achieved through manually-operated mechanical devices and flexible components. In contrast, the updating of the genre during the 1950s and 1960s tended to overcome geometric and technical boundaries with proposals designed to convey meaning, persuade people, and closely connect them with their surroundings (Oliveras, 2010). Kinetic art conceptually flourished, during this period, allowing the establishment of a more direct and reciprocal relationship between the objects and the observers, as well as between the objects and their environments. European and North American pioneers in this area included Peter Vogel, Nicolas Schöffer, Vassilakis Takis, James Seawright, and Wen-Ying Tsai. Numerous Latin American artists were also at the forefront of the kinetic art movement of this period, amongst others, Antonio Asis,

Martha Boto, Vardanega, Gertrude Goldschmidt, and Gregorio Vardanega. It has been argued that the conceptual background behind kinetic art developments was influenced by different factors in each part of the world. In North America, for example, motion was linked to the dynamicity of trends in the upcoming visual arts, cinema, and television. European endeavours were more driven by technological experimentation with novel mechanisms and materials, whilst Latin American proposals were instigated by utopian ideals of social transformation and progression (Bayon, 1974). This was connected to the arrival of modernity to Latin America, which resulted in numerous changes in all areas and prompted the search for new artistic languages to represent them. Such quests resulted in different types of expressionism; kinetic art being one of the most suggestive.

Parallel to the development of kinetic art, cybernetic theories were taking shape, attempting to explain and propose learning strategies for living organisms and machines. Norbert Wiener in the 1940s (Wiener, 1948), and later on, Gordon Pask during the 1970s (Pask, 1975), argued that living and non-living systems can both have 'purpose', hence it was possible to establish effective communication through an exchange of actions between humans and machines. These ideas lead researchers to believe that the relationship between user and space could constitute a system of continuous feedback in which the spaces may change according to the needs of people. Such beliefs fuelled kinetic art proposals that comprised, not only moving objects actuated by people, but also provided a new platform for social interaction between people and art.

A seminal example was the work of Venezuelan artists Jesus Soto, Carlos Cruz Diez, and Alejandro Otero, who took a revolutionary stand through their creations. They were actively involved in 'Los Disidentes' (The Dissidents) 1945-1950, an artistic group which opposed the political scene of Venezuela, at the time, describing it as regressive and stagnant (*Los Disidentes*, 1950). Their work sought to create new settings in which to integrate moving objects, light, colour, time, and the viewer. In such settings motion was not actuated by mechanical means, but created by the spontaneous participation of the audience. This was the case with Soto's installations entitled *Penetrables*, many of which are still in use. They consist of large prismatic steel structures from which arrays of thin, plastic tubes dangle, and through which observers can walk. Their aesthetic experience covers all senses besides sight, as they can also be touched, smelt, heard and most importantly, lived.

Another influential example for Latin America was the work of the artistic group GRAV (*Groupe de Recherche d'Art Visuel*) between 1960 and 1968. Argentinean artists Julio Le Parc, Horacio Garcia Rossi, Hugo Demarco, and Norberto Gómez, amongst other artists from Spain and France, founded GRAV in Paris. GRAV's most important contribution was to shift the emphasis from the moving object to its interpretation and experience. The interest was placed on the audience, who was actively involved in the works, as stated in their 1966 manifesto:

We are particularly interested in the proliferation of works which permit of varied situations, whether they engender a strong

visual excitement, or demand a move on the part of the spectator, or contain in themselves a principle of transformation, or whether they call for active participation from the spectator... but this is only a first stage. The second might be, for example, to produce, no longer only the works, but ensembles which would play the part of social incitement, at the same time as liberating the spectator from the obsession with possession (Stiles & Selz, 1996, p. 411).

Over the past two decades, the design of interactive-kinetic environments in Latin America has rapidly advanced in complexity, both theoretically and technically. Its inclusion as a topic of research and experimentation within architectural academic fields is becoming stronger. Sensors and actuators that monitor changes in habitable spaces are becoming widely available. In addition, with the advent of personal computers and technological empowerment to all kinds of people, more dynamic, direct, and real-time control can be achieved. But most importantly, there is a common realisation that technology is not a barrier for creativity and that truly interactive-kinetic environments do not necessarily rely on the complexity of the physical components used, but on the sophistication of the interactive strategy. This is underlined by the argument posed by various authors of a shift from a mechanical paradigm to a biological paradigm in which spaces have the ability to change as circumstances change in a more intuitive and flowing manner (Fox, 2009, p.19).

REINFORCING 'HIGH-SOCIAL'

Contemporary human changing patterns and technologically influenced lifestyles are the driving force behind new developments in interactive-kinetic environments (Fox & Kemp, 2009). As explorations become more theoretically and technically complex, gaps between artists, architects, and engineers are bridged. Very often, the boundaries between disciplines become blurred when merging choreographed motion, digital media and electronics with physical settings. In Latin-America, artists (more than architects or engineers) seem to be leading this integration. An interesting example is the work of the Argentine theatre company *Fuerzabruta* (recently named one of the top most innovative companies in South America). Their productions feature remarkable kinetic devices and great visual and lighting effects, all brought alive by audience participation. In general, the emphasis has been on the high-social aspect of the interventions, regardless of the means used to materialise the interaction, and the physical movement. In other words, the design of the social event takes priority over the type of technical tools employed to achieve it.

Latin America is a region where there is great disparity between extreme poverty and immense wealth, as well as social and political instability. However, there is still a great display of formal and technical creativity, especially in the process of formulating alternative ways to apply available resources. In this context, the appropriate integration of technical means within the design process is a determining factor for their effectiveness. On one hand, relatively high-end technology can

be accessible for the design and production of architecture; although, this technology is not always appropriated for the needs that it is attempting to address and the socio-cultural conditions where it is implemented. On the other hand, there is a growing drive to develop local, more efficient, and self-reliant technologies. This is complemented with design philosophies that fit within fiscal limitations and have the ability to take root and evolve over time. Given these conditions, the challenge is to explore potential intersections between computer-aided design, available materials and resources, new manufacturing processes and traditional crafts. This challenge drives many of the projects featured in this paper.

In some projects, the kinetic-object is used as a facilitator and not as a protagonist for the interaction. Hence, the exploration becomes less ambitious in method and more specific in scope, by using very simple components and unpretentious materials that flavour the project's discourse. This is the paradigm in *Mülltüten* (2012), an interactive urban installation by architecture students from the Universidad de Talca, Chile. Its name is a fusion of the Spanish word *mil* (a thousand), and the German word *mülltüten* (bin bag). The installation comprised of six metres high by sixty metres long waving fabric, made from a thousand black bin bags, all knotted together in the corners. Placed at the main entrance of the University of Kassel in Germany, its intention was to expose the wind as the connector integrating the campus to the city, whilst giving another value and meaning to a usually understated material.

Other projects use a range of kinetic and mechanical devices actuated by people's movements. *Solo* (2010) and *Tunnel* (2010), both by Brazilian artists Rejane Cantoni and Leonardo Crescenti (Cantoni-Crescenti), are fitting examples. *Solo* presents a surface formed by a series of interconnected panels, supported on seesaw-type mechanisms which make them unstable. As visitors walk over the surface, the panels swing from side to side, in function of the forces applied to them. Any localised movement produces repercussions on the neighbouring plates, so the entire surface moves creating waves. The purpose behind it is that the audience can interact with the project and between one-another simultaneously.

Tunnel has a similar interactive goal and also uses people's weight to induce motion. This installation is composed of 92 interlinked metal frames, supported on a central beam. As people walk through it the frames oscillate up to five degrees at either side creating undulatory movements across the entire structure. Another very interesting example was *On Space Time Foam* (2012) by Argentinean artist Tomas Saraceno. This project comprised a multi-layered space made from elastic, translucent PVC membranes, covering an area of 400 square metres, and suspended 24 meters above ground level at the *Cubo* space of the HangarBicocca in Milan, Italy. Visitors had the opportunity to access it from above, observe it from below, or penetrate an inflated air cushion formed in between. The different layers of the space were constantly activated by the changes in climate, air pressure, and participation of people. This work was inspired by *El Jardín de Senderos Que se Bifurcan* (The Garden of Forking Paths) (1941) by Argentinean

writer Jorge Luis Borges, a story in which there is no uniform or absolute time, but an infinite series of divergent, convergent, and parallel times. It was also connected to theories of quantum physics, which argue that the universe is structured like foam in which space and time change coordinates. In Saraceno's work, the symbiotic relationship between user and structure was intended as a metaphor for how human interrelations affect each other and the Earth in which we live. Hence, every step unchained a series of reactions modifying the spatial coordinates of other people and also impacting upon a 'parallel universe', represented by the spaces above or below each layer.

The work of Mexican artist Rafael Lozano-Hemmer also embodies the desire to construct not only enjoyable experiences, but also meaningful social interactions and positive reinforcement. *Homografías* (Homographies) (2006/2012), for example, comprises 144 standard white-fluorescent light-tubes hung from 72 robotic fixtures on the ceiling of a habitable space. Each 1.83 metre-long light tube revolves on its central axis using a computer-controlled stepper motor. This is linked to a surveillance tracking system of six panoptic cameras (placed on the ceiling), which detect the presence and position of people in the space. As they move, the light tubes slowly revolve generating different patterns and 'paths of light' that vary in relation to the number of people present and their actions. Every certain period of time, the tubes align forming orthogonal arrangements. Plasma screens of the walls show the tracking systems, informing people about the position of others and their effect on the behaviour of the overall system. The author argues that in many buildings, such as offices, hospitals, factories and prisons, the ubiquitous presence of fluorescent light tube creates a cold experience of functional normalisation. *Homografías* attempts to pervert this perception and offers a plurality of points of contact by generating alternating compositions.

IMPACT ON ARCHITECTURAL AND URBAN SPACE

Unlike other forms of art, interactive-kinetic installations are not suitable for reproduction on paper or digital media, nor can they have a place in a gallery or a museum in the traditional manner. Due to their size and collaborative nature with the audience, they become an integral part of the architectural and urban space. Even though most built examples have been transitory installations, they prove to have a considerable impact on habitable spaces. This suggests that they ought to be considered not just as elements placed in a space, but as architectural components. Ever since their beginnings, the fundamental rationale behind the design of interactive-kinetic environments has been to create an interface between four key ingredients: the user/audience (subject), the kinetic artefact (object), the event (experience), and the hosting space (architecture). Different aspects of interactive-kinetic environments are highlighted according to the emphasis placed on these different ingredients. For example, the complexity of the technical means used to build the kinetic components (em-

phasis on the object); the degree of physical transformation and integration with the surroundings (emphasis on the relationship object-architecture); the type of interactive encounter and the degree of interaction with the audience (emphasis on the relationship object-experience-subject); and the level of response to specific design agendas/problems (emphasis on the relationship object-architecture- subject). In design approaches that reinforce a relationship between the object and the architecture, the character given to the object is of great importance, since it would determine the intensity of the interaction. The object needs to have a certain level of sophistication or 'intelligence' in order to engage and sustain communication with the audience. On the other hand, in approaches that use the object/architecture as a medium to instigate and emphasise interaction between people within the audience, the design of the experience takes priority. This experience needs to be compelling and persuasive in order to encourage exchange amongst participants.

An example of the first scenario is *Environmental Noise Interactive Façade (ENIF)* (2009-10), developed at Universidad de los Andes. This façade was fitted with noise sensors that collected audio frequencies from the surrounding environment. In order to make the skin respond to localised noise by physically distorting specific sections of its reflective surface, Input data was managed through micro-controllers programmed with *Wiring*. The experience allowed visitors to visualise alterations in noise levels and reflect on the range of noise pollution in the local environment. Another case is *Fachada* (2012) by Antoni-Crescenti, an interactive-kinetic installation fixed on the main façade of the *Espacio Fundación Telefónica* Building in Buenos Aires, Argentina. The installation is made from 75 thin aluminium strips, which in sequence swivel 90 degrees back and forth. Initially, all strips are placed perpendicular to the façade. When a pedestrian approaches the building its presence is detected by sensors located at the ends of the façade. This starts up a mechanism comprising a short steel plate which slides over a rail at the bottom of the aluminium strips, whilst progressively pushing them into a parallel position to the façade. When the plate has passed, the strips go back to their original arrangement pulled by a weight-driven mechanism. The strips have a matt finish on the inside and a reflective mirror-like finish on the outside. As they move, they reflect the surroundings establishing a dialog between people inside and outside the building. The interaction continuously changes according to the flow of people moving in front of the building and the conditions of the environment that is reflected.

Although most of the examples shown so far in this paper are or were temporary installations proposed by artists, there is a growing interest in the subject between architects and engineers (especially within academia). This suggests that it could only be a matter of time before interactive-kinetic environments could be explored as permanent or more common features of buildings. In addition, there is currently an active debate within the design community, which has raised a range of still unresolved questions. For example: 'Can interactive-kinetic environments form part of everyday spaces?'; 'Are all types of interactions suitable for the Latin-American context?;

and, Is the technology used fitting for the local context?'. These questions stirred two explorations, *Guayering* and *Colorama*, developed at Universidad de Los Andes by two groups of Master students, lead by the first author of this paper. The main drive for these explorations was to ground an interactive-kinetic environment in the internalisation of an existing everyday space. This with the aim of highlighting and enhancing the elements and structures of the environment that often go unnoticed by their constant, daily, and habitual presence. In fact, during the theoretical development of the proposals, it was noted that, although there have been several projects of interactive-kinetic environments located in everyday spaces, much of the experimentation had concentrated on the search for new forms and devices of interaction and movement. However, there has been little exploration of the potential in utilising primary characteristics of customary spaces in order to transform them into interactive-kinetic environments. The two projects, subsequently presented, were designed based on evolutionary patterns of growth and strategies of behaviour that would allow them to adapt to the actions of their inhabitants/actors.

Guayering (2012), named from an adaptation of the Spanish word *guaya* (wire), aimed to augment and mediate human experience, interaction and perception through the use of a temporary envelope that changed the meaning and function of an existing space. The project consisted of an enclosure made from a large white elastic fabric suspended from thirty points, sixteen of which were linked to two mobiles made from rectangular aluminium profiles and steel wire. Each mobile was linked to a pulley and connected to a standard manually-operated crank-mechanism, which allowed people passing by to raise it up or lower it down. During this process, the enclosure progressively transformed increasing or decreasing the size of the inhabited space. Consequently, the level of intimacy and closeness between people was constantly altered. As the space became smaller, inside users could pull on plastic bottles filled with coloured ink that were attached to the fabric. Through this action, the ink progressively tainted the enclosure exposing the degree of interaction between the object and the user. The experience was designed in order to make the audience aware of the impact that their actions may have on others.

The project was monitored for ten days through the collection of quantitative and qualitative data aimed to evaluate the complexity and richness of the observations, associations, and perceptions that the users constructed during their experience. Amongst other things, it was found that certain groups of audiences, such as young children, tended to interact more freely with the space, pushing its physical boundaries to the limit. They appeared not to be intimidated when the space became smaller, forcing them to get closer. University students, instead, used the movable devices as an excuse to communicate with each other through physical or verbal actions. For example, some would make the fabric drop on purpose over their classmates, in order to instigate their reaction. In contrast, some adults only stopped to observe others interacting with the environment.

Figure 1-3. *Guayering*, details of the proposal's components. Photos: Oscar Prieto

Figure 4-6. *Guayering*, Mechanisms used to actuate the mobiles and textile. Photos: Oscar Prieto

Figure 7-11. *Guayering*, interaction during evaluation period. Photos: Oscar Prieto

Colorama (2013) intended to underline an everyday passageway, through the play of light, colour and shadow, whilst empowering pedestrians as active agents of their changing environment and enriching their experience. The project was placed on a highly transited and glass-enclosed bridge that connects two buildings of the University Campus. The bridge frames a privileged view of Bogota's city centre on one side and a prominent view of the Andes Mountains on the other. However, during a primary study of the space it was noticed that people passing by very rarely became aware of or gave importance to these views. Hence, the first objective of the project was to transform the traditional relationships established between people, and the immediate physical context of the bridge, by highlighting the views through spinning coloured elements. Ninety of these elements were placed on both sides of the bridge. Each one was built with four pieces of 36 centimetre-long coloured acrylics forming a swastika paddle wheel. They were designed to be manually rotated, generating changing coloured patterns and lighting effects inside the bridge. The second objective of the proposal was to change the existing

perception of the bridge of being a purely transit space by encouraging people to stop and interact with the environment and with each other. In order to achieve this, the colour paddle wheels were framed by large black board surfaces where people could express themselves through writing or drawing. This interaction built new relationships between passers-by that stopped to write a message or read, add, oppose or discuss someone else's message, which in turn helped to establish an open and evolving communication flow. Day by day the space was enriched and transformed by new interventions. During the monitoring period it was noticed that, in general, the users responded to the proposal as it was originally imagined, by spinning the swastika elements. Many stopped and observed the city through the different colours; others just enjoyed the tactile experience of moving the elements. When pedestrians realised the possibility of writing on the panels, the number of them who stopped inside the project significantly increased. At this point the project began a more drastic transformation, by inciting further, and unexpected, social interaction between participants.

Figure 12-16. *Colorama*, proposal's components. Photos:12,16 Oscar Prieto, 13,14,15 Crystian Melo

Some iconic kinetic interactive environments using advanced technological systems have generated the wrong impression: that in this field there is only room for advanced technology or high economic resources. One of the challenges of *Guayering* and *Colorama* experiments was to demonstrate precisely that it was possible to obtain environments with the desired level of interaction, even without the use of complex or expensive strategies. Undoubtedly the integration of technology in the design of interactive kinetic environments may represent a key component to create a more effective interaction. However, some amongst the more prominent theorists in the field pose a demystification of the role of technology within interaction design. Interaction is not a specific field of computers: 'one can create something interactive yet not hi-tech – likewise one

can create something hi-tech yet not the slightest bit interactive' (Haque, 2006).

NEW HORIZONS

The examples presented here are a tester of the type of interactive-kinetic environments being currently developed in Latin America or by Latin American designers abroad. They represent the aspiration to enhance and mediate a diversity of human encounters through engaging and transformative built environments, where appropriated technology and local technology are very much complementary. A growing interest in the subject makes this a very current, vibrant,

Figure 17-20. *Colorama*, interaction during evaluation period. Photos:17,18 Oscar Prieto, 19 Eduard Romero, 20 Carolina Rodriguez

exiting, and evolving field. This is evident in the increasing support by different organisations and practices, which sponsor events and design competition targeting the development of innovative interactive-kinetic environments. The Young Architects Program (YAP) is an example, launched by CONSTRUCTO together with The Museum of Modern Art (MoMA), which aimed to create new opportunities for talented Latin American architects to think, explore, and improve the quality of collective-use spaces. The project *Water Cathedral* (2012) by GUN Arquitectos, winner of the YAP, illustrates the tendencies developing amongst upcoming new generations. Built in the walled forecourt of Matucana 100, in Santiago de Chile, this intervention formed a dynamic forest of tapered white fabric bags, suspended from steel frames that sway gently, oozing water as people stroll through. This is yet another testimony of Latin-American emerging architecture concerned with providing novel and sensible design solutions, whilst embracing social needs, aspirations and diversity of expression. Various authors argue that Latin America in the new millennium is: “witnessing the passage from a difficult adolescence to a state

of grace and plenitude also visible in economic, social, and political optimism (Ábalos, 2011, p. 16).

In this context, the challenges that designers are presented with include learning from cultural heritage and traditional techniques, and responding to unique cultural and environmental conditions, whilst remaining current and becoming more visible to the outside world. In regards to interactive-kinetic environments, the lack of resources has become, more than a barrier, an opportunity for creativity and innovation that can be applied and openly enjoyed in everyday spaces. In most cases, technology plays a secondary role, mediating between the social and cultural aspects of the interaction, which are the protagonists.

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